

Studies in Biheterocycles. Part-I. Formylation of 2-(2'-Thienyl) Indole*

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Synthesis and formylation of 2-(2'-thienyl) indole are reported. Formylation studies indicate that the 2-thienyl ring is deactivated and formylation occurs only at position 3 of the indole ring.

OUR interest in the potential pharmacologically active compounds with both indole and nitro-furan ring systems has led us to study the electrophilic substitution reactions of 2-(2'-thienyl) indole (II). This compound was prepared by the polyphosphoric acid catalysed cyclisation of 2-acetylthiophene-phenylhydrazone (I) and was subjected to formylation according to the method of Tyson and Shaw¹ as modified by Smith² employing 0.011 mole of 1:1 complex of dimethylformamide and phosphorus-oxychloride (Vilsmeier type reagent) and 0.01 mole of indole in excess of dimethylformamide. A monoaldehyde (III) was obtained and was characterised by the preparation of its 2,4-dinitro-phenylhydrazone.

The IR spectrum of indole (II) showed a sharp band at 3425 cm⁻¹ characteristic of indole N-H stretching frequency, while in the case of aldehyde (III) the N-H stretching frequency was found shifted to 3150 cm⁻¹ as a broad band and the carbonyl stretching frequency was seen at 1630 cm⁻¹ as expected for an indole-3-carboxaldehyde³.

Although it is known that both indole¹⁻² and thiophene⁴ undergo formylation reaction separately under slightly different conditions, our studies show that indole is more reactive than thiophene during electrophilic substitution reactions. Use of excess formylating reagent under different conditions

did not effect any further formylation. This non-formylation of 2-thienyl ring of indole (II) may probably be due to its deactivation because of its positive charge created by the attack of electrophile at position 3 of the indole ring and conjugation in analogy with the deactivation of 2-phenyl ring in the nitration of 2-phenylindole⁵.

The compound II displays an interesting property. A pale yellow solution of this indole in chloroform turns blue on exposure to sunlight for a minute or two, while a solution in carbon tetrachloride gives a green precipitate. This photochemical reaction of the indole (II), which is under investigation appears to involve position 3 of the indole ring because the corresponding aldehyde (III) does not undergo a similar reaction.

Experimental

2-(2'-Thienyl) indole (II) :

2-Acetylthiophenephenylhydrazone (I, 10 g.) was slowly added with vigorous stirring to the polyphosphoric acid (prepared from 50 g of phosphorus pentoxide and 30 ml of phosphoric acid) maintained at 95°. The temperature rose spontaneously to 105° and the mixture was maintained at 110°-115° for a period of 1 hr by external heating. The resulting sticky brown mass obtained after cooling was poured onto finely crushed ice when crude 2-(2'-thienyl) indole (II) separated as a grey mass. It was filtered, washed with water and dried. This crude indole was purified by passing through a column of alumina in benzene. It was recrystallised from benzene-petroleum ether (60°-80°) mixture into cream yellow needles, m.p. 169°, yield, 7.1 g. (Found : C, 72.16; H, 4.36; N, 6.84. C₁₂H₉NS requires C, 72.36; H, 4.52; N, 7.03%).

2-(2'-Thienyl) indole-3-carboxaldehyde (III) :

a) (Using 1:1 mole of indole and formylating reagent).

2-(2'-Thienyl) indole (II) (2.0 g, 0.01 mole) in dimethyl formamide (1 ml) was added below 20° to the formylating reagent prepared in usual manner

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from dimethylformamide (3.2 ml) and phosphorusoxychloride (1 ml, 0.011 mole). The resulting reaction mixture was warmed and maintained at 30° for 45 mins. It was then poured onto crushed ice and was basified by adding 9% sodium hydroxide when 2-(2'-thienyl) indole-3-carboxaldehyde separated. It was collected by filtration, washed and crystallised from ethyl alcohol into pale yellow needles. Yield, 2 g., m.p. 238° (Found : C, 68.52; H, 3.72; N, 6.04. C₁₃H₉NOS requires C, 68.72; H, 3.96; N, 6.16%).

2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone of 2-(2'-thienyl) indole-3-carboxaldehyde was obtained as blood red micro crystals, m.p. 325°-326° d (Found : N, 16.80. C₁₉H₁₃N₅O₄S requires N, 17.19%).

b) (Using 1 : 2 mole of indole and formylating reagent).

The reaction was carried out exactly as above using (II) (2.0 g; 0.010 mole) in dimethylformamide (1 ml) and formylating reagent prepared from phosphorusoxychloride (2 ml, 0.022 mole) and dimethylformamide (6.4 ml). The product (2.0 g.) was crystallised from ethyl alcohol as pale yellow needles, m.p. 238°. It did not show any depression in melting point when mixed with the sample (III) prepared as in (a) ν N-H, 3150 cm⁻¹, ν C=O 1630 cm⁻¹.

c) (By heating indole with excess formylating reagent)

A mixture of (II) (2.0 g., 0.010 mole) in dimethylformamide (1 ml) was heated over a waterbath for 45 mins. with the formylating reagent prepared from phosphorusoxychloride (4 ml., 0.044 mole) and dimethylformamide (12.8 ml). The product after the usual work up was found to be the aldehyde III, as identified by m.p. and superimposable I.R.

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